

CONSTRUCTION AND MAINTENANCE OF TIRES USED IN AUTOMOBILES

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Abstract: Changes in tire production, tire types, wear of tire tread under operating conditions, maintenance and repair of tires, repair of tires in the conditions of a motor transport enterprise.

Key words: Tire profile view, regular profile, wide profile, low profile, ultra-low profile, arched, pneumatic, diagonal and radial, tire tread operation, dynamic imbalance, tire recovery, tube repair.

It is also divided into types by the appearance, dimensions, construction and method of ensuring hermetrization of the tire profile.

Light car tires are used in all climatic regions, passenger cars, light trucks, minibuses. For the same operational conditions, tires are used on trucks, their trailers, semi-trailers, buses [1].

According to the appearance of the tire profile (Fig. 1), they are divided into simple profile, wide profile, low profile, ultra-low profile, arc-shaped, pneumatic tires.

In normal profile tires (Fig. 2), the ratio of height H to width B is greater than 0.9. Its cross-section is in the form of a torpid, and it can be made with or without a chamber. Tires of this type are installed on all vehicles designed for driving on good roads [2].

Figure 1. Appearance of tire treads.

In turn, radial tires are divided into R and RS types. In diagonal tires (Fig. 3, a), there are two layers of cord threads and they are located along the diagonal of the tire. The structure of the rest of its parts is the same as that of a radial (R) tire.

In radial (R) tires (Fig. 3, b) cord threads are located along two radii, twice less than in diagonal tires. For it, H/B is $0.7 \div 0.85$ and it is made with or without a camera.

Figure 2. Tire shear.
B-tire width; H-profile height; D-tire outer diameter; d-the diameter of the beam.

Figure 3. Construction of diagonal and radial tires.
a) diagonal; b) radial.

Compared to the diagonal type, radial tires are distinguished by the ability to carry a larger load, greater radial elasticity, less rolling resistance, relatively less heat, and twice as much durability. However, radial tires have disadvantages such as high cost, high lateral elasticity, noise when driving on uneven roads [3-4].

Tires are considered one of the most expensive elements of the car, they affect the dynamics of the traction-stop mechanisms of the car, stability, smooth running, fuel economy, and traffic safety. Failure of tires and reduction of service life is related to violation of the rules of technical use.

The main reasons for premature failure of tires (Fig. 4) are increased internal pressure, low pressure, incorrect alignment of the wheels, crushing of the brake drum into an egg shape, non-uniform operation of the brake mechanisms, excessive overloading, tires hitting sharp-edged objects, not changing seats on time, poor driving skills, changing road and climatic conditions, etc [5-6].

Figure 4. Tire tread wear under operating conditions.

a-protective normal eating; b-increasing the angle of approach (right front wheel, rear view); v-tire internal pressure increase from the norm; g-reduction of the internal pressure of the tire; d-decreasing the approach angle from the norm; e-decreasing the deviation angle of the front wheel from the norm (right front wheel,

rear view); *j*-wheel balance exceeding the permissible value; *z*-increasing the deviation angle of the front wheel from the norm (left front wheel, rear view); *i*-reduction of the angle of deviation of the rear wheel from the norm (rear right wheel, rear view); *k*-the result of wheel slippage.

Inspection of car tires consists of checking the air pressure in the tire, checking the outer side and determining the tread wear, removing three things from it, checking the distance between the paired tires (40-50 mm), and replacing them. In order to determine and adjust the air pressure in the tire, it is possible to obtain compressed air from electric, hand and foot pumps, as well as from devices with fixed or mobile compressors (Fig. 5). The production capacity of compressor equipment is 1 m³□min, and the pressure it creates is equal to 1.0-1.2 Mpa [6].

Figure 5. Equipment used for inflating car tires:
a-fixed compressor; b-hand pump; c-foot pump; d-moving compressor

The tire maintenance process is as follows:

- check their internal pressure during diagnostics and bring the internal pressure to normal during the 1st technical service;
- inspecting tires, determining edge wear, cleaning objects stuck to the coating and between them, checking the depth;

- balancing the tires with or without removing them from the car during technical service.

In order for tires to work better, special attention should be paid to their disassembly and assembly. For this, stands for disassembling and assembling wheels (Fig. 6) and many types of non-standard equipment are used. They are mainly composed of an electric motor, a reducer, a compressor, cranes and other details [7].

6-rasm. G'ildiraklarni bo'laklarga ajratish va yig'ish stendlari ko'rinishi

Before assembly of tires, discs and wheel details (board and lock rings) are checked, and they are cleaned of dirt and rust. Special machines are used for straightening and cleaning discs.

Special equipment is also used for separating and assembling the wheels of trucks and buses [8-9].

It is necessary to balance car tires after disassembling and assembling them.

Wheel balancing should be done when a new tire is installed and at every 2nd maintenance. Taking into account the peculiarities of the operation of movable and fixed equipment, recommend static balancing movable equipment in the shingle assembly workshops of large taxi motor sheds and in the 2nd maintenance zone, static balancing in the 1st maintenance zone possible.

In order to eliminate the static imbalance, the loads-8 are installed on both sides of the disk. To eliminate the dynamic imbalance, the loads are installed diagonally on both sides (Fig. 7b, v). The above process is performed 1-2 times in order to accurately perform balancing [9].

Figure 7. Movable balancing device.

Dynamic balancing work is very difficult, because it is impossible to keep the sensor in constant contact with the base brake shoe. Recently, foreign companies have been producing only static balancing equipment. High-level workers are required to work on moving equipment.

Static balancing can be done without equipment, for this a wheel is installed on a light rotating stand. The heaviest part of the wheel is always at the bottom. The bags installed on the opposite side are replaced until the end of this situation. This method is recommended for balancing the wheels of trucks and buses [10].

Modern stationary equipment performs the work of balancing wheels without dividing them into static and dynamic types.

First of all, the lightest place on the outer side of the wheel is determined, and then on the other side. In some models of equipment, the imbalance on both sides can be detected at the same time. Moving equipment performs balancing one after the other, first statically, then dynamically. The operating instructions of the moving equipment (Fig. 7-a) are as follows: the suspended car wheel-4, the equipment is rotated with the help of an electric motor-1 with a frequency corresponding to a speed of 120-170 km/h. The sensor-7 attached to the car's lower suspension arm-6 or the main brake lever converts the vibration of the wheel into an electrical signal. Impulses impacting the mounting surface of the sensor are sent to the measuring device of the device. The value of the necessary amount of balancing load is determined using the indicator-3, which shows pulse amplitudes. Including pulses will cause stroboscope lamp-2 to start. When it burns, the wheel seems to be standing still. the illuminated point is remembered, and when the wheel stops spinning, its heaviest place is determined [11].

Repair of tires in the conditions of a motor transport enterprise. Depending on the damage and wear of the tires, they are repaired by removing local damage (holes, tears) or gluing a new tread. Pasting of new treads on tires is carried out in tire repair factories or large automobile transport enterprises. Tire restoration is divided into 2 groups:

- repair of tires that are not completely torn (punctured),
- repair of completely torn tires.

Repairing a tire, installing a new tread, and reusing it will reduce the cost of tires by 4-8 times [12].

Repair of tires is carried out in the following order:

1. Acceptance of tires for repair - when accepting tires, it is determined whether they are suitable for repair or not, and the cost and scope of work for their repair is determined.

2. Preparation for repair consists of washing and drying tires. Washed tires are dried in special drying cabinets at a temperature of 40-60 °C for 24 hours.

3. Tire cutting - Damaged rubber and carcass parts are cut conically at an angle of 45°- 60°. Depending on the place of damage, they can be trimmed in three ways: the trimmed tires are dried in drying cabinets at a temperature of 50-60 °C.

4. Surface roughening - surfaces to be glued are roughened for better adhesion, for this purpose special roughening machines are used.

5. Applying glue - applying glue to the surface is done using a brush or sprayer. When spraying, glue adheres to the entire surface with the same thickness [13-14].

Apply 2 times with the help of a brush, first apply glue in the ratio of 1:8 or 1:10 (1 part of adhesive rubber to 8 or 10 parts of gasoline), then apply glue in the ratio of 1:5. Wait until the glue dries.

6. Closing the hole - done in 2 ways: gluing layer by layer or plugging.

In the case of layer-by-layer gluing - thin rubber with a thickness of 0.7...0.9 mm is glued to the hole, after which unripened rubber with a thickness of 2 mm is successively glued [14].

Plugging - in this method, a cut is removed from the frame and a specially cut cord is inserted into the hole. This work is very difficult. Therefore, it is not widely used.

7. Patching - patching after closing the holes. Patching ensures that the materials are firmly connected to each other. It is necessary to be able to choose the compression pressure, temperature and time for quality patching.

Repair of cameras at motor transport enterprises - cameras are patched after determining their suitability for work. Serviceable cameras have no hardened areas, tear areas should not exceed 50 mm in length and 5 mm in width. Holes are patched by applying a 1:8 concert ratio glue to regular or unripened rubber and sticking it to the tear. Ordinary rubber is roughened on a wheel, glue is applied to the hole, and it is patched with an 8:10 mm unripened rubber on its edges. Chambers are pressed on plates using special clamps and patched for 15-20 minutes [15].

References

1. Sh.P. Magdiyev "Technical operation and service of automobiles" Tashkent, 2021.
2. Sh.P. Magdiyev "Car construction, service and repair of car engines" Tashkent, 2021.
3. Magdiyev, S. P., Kadirshayev, T., & Rakhmatov, M. I. (2023). CAR ENGINE LUBRICATION SYSTEM MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(2), 250-260.
4. Avliyokulov, J. S., Pulatovich, M. S., & Rakhmatov, M. I. (2023). MAIN FAILURES OF THE VEHICLE BRAKE SYSTEM, MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR. *CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES*, 4(3), 63-69.
5. Magdiyev Shovkat Pulatovich and Murodjon Iskandarovich Rakhmatov. "MALFUNCTIONS OF INJECTION ENGINES THAT OCCURRED ON THE ROADS AND THEIR PREVENTION." *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal* 1.7 (2023): 95-100.
6. Magdiyev Shovkat Pulatovich, Rakhmatov Murodjon Iskandarovich, & Sharopov Zavqiddin Zayniddinovich. (2023). MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR OF TRANSMISSION UNITS AND MECHANISMS. *Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal*, 1(4), 181–191.

7. Рискүлов, Алимжон Ахмаджанович, Жамшед Садуллоевич Авлиёкулов, and Мурод Искандарович Рахматов. "РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ ФЕНОМЕНА НАНОСОСТОЯНИЯ ПРОМЫШЛЕННЫХ ТЕРМОПЛАСТОВ." Вестник науки и образования 12-1 (115) (2021): 38-40.

8. Riskulov, Alimjon Axmadjanovich, Xurshidbek Ikromovich Nurmetov, and Murod Iskandarovich Rakhmatov. "Damping Materials Based On" Thermoelastoplast-Thermoplast" Mixtures For The Structures Of Tractor Units." The American Journal of Engineering and Technology 3.05 (2021): 116-125.

9. Magdiyev Shovkat Pulatovich, & Rakhmatov Murodjon Iskandarovich. (2023). THE SEQUENCE OF MAINTENANCE OF THE SUPPLY SYSTEM OF THE DIESEL ENGINE. Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal, 1(7), 47–57.

10. Rakhmatov Murodjon Iskandarovich, Sharopov Zavqiddin Zayniddinovich, and Boliyev Mansur Tuygunovich. "CONSTRUCTION OF A FUEL SUPPLY SYSTEM FOR VEHICLES RUNNING ON COMPRESSED GAS AND THEIR MAINTENANCE." Nexus: World of Scientific news in Science International Journal Vol 1 Issue 1 (2023): 54-65.

11. Magdiyev Shovkat Pulatovich, Rakhmatov Murodjon Iskandarovich, & Sharopov Zavqiddin Zayniddinovich. "CAR BATTERY STRUCTURE AND MAINTENANCE." Nexus: World of Scientific news in Science International Journal Vol 1 Issue 1 (2023): 66-73.

12. Khakimova, Nilufar Juraevna, and Murod Iskandarovich Rakhmatov. "Projections With Numeral Marks. Projections of a Point and a Straight Line. Mutual Position of Straight Lines." Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science 3.5 (2022): 267-269.

13. Avlyyokulov, J. S., M. Rakhmatov, and R. D. Tadzhiev. "Requirements for Transmission, Steering Gears Control And Suspension of the Carher for Hot Climate Conditions." Texas Journal of Engineering and Technology 14 (2022): 4-6.

14. Zayniddinovich, Sharopov Zavqiddin, Boliyev Mansur Tuygunovich, and Murodjon Iskandarovich Rakhmatov. "The Main Malfunctions that Occur in the Engine's Krivoship Shatun and Gas Distribution Mechanisms." CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MATHEMATICAL THEORY AND COMPUTER SCIENCES 3.11 (2022): 47-50.

15. Magdiyev, Shovkat Pulatovich, Turgunbay Kadirshayev, and Murodjon Iskandarovich Rakhmatov. "CAR ENGINE LUBRICATION SYSTEM MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR." Modern Scientific Research International Scientific Journal 1.2 (2023): 250-260.